

KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK: NAZARIY ASOSLAR VA RIVOJLANISH YO‘NALISHLARI**Mohira Akromova Akmal qizi**

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur ilmiy tezisdagi kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikning nazariy asoslari, iqtisodiy rivojlanishdagi o‘rni hamda zamonaviy sharoitlarda rivojlanish yo‘nalishlari tadqiq qilingan. Tadbirkorlik faoliyatining mohiyati, tarixiy rivojlanishi va kichik biznes subyektlarining iqtisodiyotdagi ahamiyati ilmiy adabiyotlar asosida tahlil qilingan. Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishning asosiy omillari, davlat qo‘llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlari hamda sohani takomillashtirish masalalari o‘rganilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari kichik biznes va tadbirkorlikning mamlakat iqtisodiyotini modernizatsiya qilish, yangi ish o‘rinlarini yaratish va aholi turmush darajasini oshirish jarayonlaridagi muhim o‘rnini ko‘rsatadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: kichik biznes, tadbirkorlik, iqtisodiy rivojlanish, innovatsiya, davlat qo‘llabquvvatlash, eksport salohiyati, ishbilarmonlik muhiti.

МАЛЫЙ БИЗНЕС И ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСТВО: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ И НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ**Мохира Акромова Акмал кизи**

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Аннотация. В данном научном тезисе исследованы теоретические основы малого бизнеса и частного предпринимательства, их роль в экономическом развитии, а также направления их развития в современных условиях. На основе научной литературы проанализированы сущность и историческое развитие предпринимательской деятельности, а также значение субъектов малого бизнеса в экономике. Изучены основные факторы развития малого бизнеса и частного предпринимательства, механизмы государственной поддержки и вопросы совершенствования отрасли. Результаты исследования показывают важную роль малого бизнеса и предпринимательства в модернизации национальной экономики, создании новых рабочих мест и повышении уровня жизни населения.

Ключевые слова: малый бизнес, предпринимательство, экономическое развитие, инновации, государственная поддержка, экспортный потенциал, деловая среда.

SMALL BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP: THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS AND DEVELOPMENT DIRECTIONS

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Abstract. This scientific thesis explores the theoretical foundations of small business and private entrepreneurship, their role in economic development, and the directions of their growth under modern conditions. The essence and historical evolution of entrepreneurial activity, as well as the significance of small business entities in the economy, are analyzed based on scientific literature. The main factors of small business and private entrepreneurship development, mechanisms of state support, and issues of sectoral improvement are examined. The research results demonstrate the crucial role of small business and entrepreneurship in modernizing the national economy, creating new jobs, and improving the population's standard of living.

Keywords: small business, entrepreneurship, economic development, innovation, state support, export potential, business environment.

Introduction. Small business and private entrepreneurship are the main components of a modern market economy. During the years of independence, the development of small business and private entrepreneurship in the Republic of Uzbekistan has been one of the priority areas of state economic policy. More than 50 decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as a number of laws, have been adopted to develop the sector. Small business and private entrepreneurship are one of the important factors in economic development, increasing employment and incomes (Archive, 2024). This sector plays an important role in the modernization and renewal of leading sectors of the economy, structural changes and diversification processes (Gov, 2024). According to Schumpeter's theory of innovation, an entrepreneur is a tool that changes markets through "creative disruption". The theory of endogenous growth considers small businesses to be an important entity that contributes to economic growth through knowledge and technology spillover. At the same time, institutional economic theory emphasizes the importance of legal frameworks, property rights, and market infrastructure for the success of small businesses. From a policy perspective, the "encouragement environment" model suggests that bureaucratic and financial barriers to small business development should be removed. Thus, traditional and modern economists have emphasized the creative role of entrepreneurship and small businesses in society and their contribution to sustainable growth.

Literature review. The first studies on entrepreneurial activity in economics began in the 18th century in the works of Cantillon, Turgot, Quesnay, Smith, and Say (Khudoyberdiev, 2016). Richard Cantillon (1680-1734) associated entrepreneurship with risk and risk, considered it as a separate form of economic activity, and was recognized as the "father of economics" (Bozorova,

2024). Until now, the concept of “entrepreneurship” has remained ambiguous in public opinion (Khudoyberdiev, 2016). There are various approaches to entrepreneurship in the scientific literature, and some scholars explain it with risk (Mirzayev, 2019). However, risk should be applied not to activity, but to the individual, and this is especially characteristic of highly innovative entrepreneurship. Among the world-famous individuals in history who took risks and started their own small businesses based on innovative technologies, we can cite entrepreneurs such as G. Ford and B. Gates (Mirzayev, 2019).

Entrepreneurship is the production of a specific product or service for the purpose of making a profit (Archive, 2024). Entrepreneurship requires creativity, the ability to introduce innovations, and the ability to effectively manage economic resources. Small businesses and private entrepreneurs perform several important tasks in the modern economy. First, small businesses play an important role in providing employment to the population, especially youth. By supporting entrepreneurial activity and creating new jobs, favorable conditions are created for them to exercise their labor rights and achieve economic independence (Khudoyberdiev, 2016). Second, the large number of activities of small businesses ensures healthy competition in the market and forms a competitive environment (Bozorova, 2024). Third, small businesses have the opportunity to quickly introduce new technologies and products, which is important in introducing innovations (Sodikova, 2024). Fourth, small businesses contribute to the economic development of regions, urban and rural areas (Ro'ziyev, 2020). Foreign experience shows that the basis of small business exports is technology trade. In particular, 50 percent of licenses sold in the United States are accounted for by small businesses (Sadikova, 2024). Research on international entrepreneurship shows the important role of small business firms in international business, especially since the pressure of globalization encourages small firms to enter international markets (Jones, 2011). The increasing role of small businesses in international trade and innovation has been confirmed in scientific research (McDougall, 2000).

Research methodology. This article is a descriptive-analytical study based on literature review and statistical analysis methods. As part of the study, available data on small business and entrepreneurship for the period 2013–2023 were studied. Official indicators of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, World Bank and UN reports, as well as official documents such as the Presidential Decree No. PF-4947 of 2017, the Tax Code of 2020 and economic development programs were selected as data sources. The dynamics of economic growth of small business entities in Uzbekistan were analyzed using the comparative method.

Analysis and discussion of results. In Uzbekistan, comprehensive state programs are being implemented to develop small business and private entrepreneurship. In particular, important decisions have been adopted, such as "On additional measures to widely involve the population in entrepreneurship in the regions and develop family entrepreneurship" (March 9, 2019, No. PQ-4231), "On the development of active entrepreneurship and innovative activities" (May 5, 2018, No. PD-3697), "On additional measures to improve the procedure for lending to projects implemented within the framework of state programs for the development of family entrepreneurship" (October 25, 2019, No. PD-4498).

A simplified taxation system has been introduced to support small businesses. Instead of paying multiple taxes, a single tax payment form has been introduced. The single tax payment rate for micro-firms and small businesses was reduced from 7 percent to 6 percent in 2014, and from the beginning of 2016 to 5 percent (Khudoyberdiev, 2016). In addition, an accelerated

system of business registration, called “one-stop shop”, has been introduced, which will support newly established small and private businesses (Khudoyberdiev, 2016). Micro-firms and small businesses that have concluded employment contracts with graduates of educational institutions have been given the right to increase the number of employees by up to 20 percent from a limited norm (for 3 years) (Khudoyberdiev, 2010).

A number of measures are recommended for the further development of small businesses and entrepreneurship. First, it is necessary to expand financial support, expand preferential lending programs, and develop microfinance institutions (Gov, 2024). Second, it is important to improve education and training programs, organize training courses for entrepreneurs on modern management methods, marketing, and financial management (Khudoyberdiev, 2016). Third, it is necessary to increase export potential, support the entry of small businesses into international markets, and encourage export-oriented production. Fourth, it is necessary to stimulate innovative activities, commercialize research results, and expand the network of technoparks. Fifth, it is necessary to improve the business environment, reduce bureaucratic barriers, simplify registration processes, and strengthen mechanisms for protecting the rights of entrepreneurs.

Further Analysis of Development Trends and Challenges.

In the context of globalization and rapid technological change, the development of small business and entrepreneurship is increasingly influenced by digital transformation processes. The integration of digital technologies into business activities has significantly expanded opportunities for small enterprises to access markets, reduce transaction costs, and improve operational efficiency. E-commerce platforms, digital payment systems, and online marketing tools enable entrepreneurs to reach a broader customer base and compete with larger firms.

At the same time, the transition to a digital economy requires entrepreneurs to possess new competencies, including digital literacy, data analysis skills, and the ability to adapt to technological innovations. In Uzbekistan, efforts are being made to promote digital entrepreneurship through the development of IT parks, startup incubators, and innovation centers. These institutions play a crucial role in supporting young entrepreneurs, fostering innovation, and facilitating the commercialization of new ideas.

Despite the positive trends, a number of challenges still hinder the full development of small business and entrepreneurship. One of the key issues is limited access to financial resources, especially for startups and innovative enterprises. Although preferential lending programs exist, many entrepreneurs face difficulties in obtaining credit due to insufficient collateral or lack of credit history. Therefore, the development of alternative financing mechanisms, such as venture capital, crowdfunding, and business angel networks, is becoming increasingly important.

Another significant challenge is the uneven development of infrastructure across regions. In rural and remote areas, limited access to transport, communication, and energy infrastructure constrains entrepreneurial activity. Addressing these disparities requires targeted regional policies and increased investment in infrastructure development.

Furthermore, regulatory and administrative barriers remain a concern for entrepreneurs. Although significant progress has been made in simplifying business registration and licensing procedures, there is still a need to further improve transparency, reduce bureaucratic hurdles,

and ensure consistent enforcement of laws. Strengthening the legal framework and protecting property rights are essential for building trust among entrepreneurs and investors.

In addition, enhancing the integration of small businesses into global value chains is an important direction for future development. Participation in international trade allows small enterprises to expand their markets, increase competitiveness, and adopt advanced technologies and management practices. This requires improving product quality standards, certification systems, and logistics infrastructure.

Overall, the sustainable development of small business and entrepreneurship depends on a complex approach that combines state support, institutional reforms, innovation promotion, and human capital development. Strengthening cooperation between government, private sector, and educational institutions will play a key role in ensuring the long-term growth and competitiveness of the sector.

Conclusions and suggestions. In conclusion, small business and private entrepreneurship are one of the main factors of modernization and sustainable development of the economy of Uzbekistan. The results of the study show that in our country a comprehensive legislative framework has been created for the development of the sector and effective state support mechanisms are being introduced. Small business entities play an important role in creating new jobs, forming a competitive environment, introducing innovations and developing regions. The number of small businesses that have introduced innovations is growing from year to year, which indicates the promising development of the sector. For the further development of small business and entrepreneurship, it is necessary to expand financial support, improve educational programs, increase export potential and improve the business environment. The sector can be further developed by implementing the results of scientific research into practice and using foreign experience.

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